

DEVELOPMENT OF LOGICAL COMPETENCES OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS BASED ON CREATIVE APPROACH

Bakhriddin Olimov

Doctoral student of Gulistan State University

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the methodology of developing the logical competencies of future elementary school teachers based on a creative approach. Effective methods of developing logical competences of future elementary school teachers are described.*

Keywords: *logical competence, development, credit-module system, professional personnel, ability to think, creativity.*

Introduction. Training of personnel in the National Program, the Concept of general secondary education and state standards in the goals of various aspects of the education and training of students, including, and above all, in the conditions of extracurricular activities, to strengthen the attention to the historical and cultural heritage. the demand is pushed forward. Extracurricular activities, especially activities related to the study of the history of the culture of their country, are necessary for the growing generation. First of all, he is actively interested in culture; able to develop intellectually and creatively in the process of cognitive activity (controlled or independent), to formalize the knowledge he is intellectually and creatively acquiring, to share his knowledge and impressions with others about his intellectual-creative "product" - of course, refers to the age-appropriate orientation of high school students who are able to share in social-communicative conditions, in particular, the introduction of a differentiated approach to education in accordance with the abilities and capabilities of students.

In order to implement the rules of the state education policy on the development of the intellectual and creative potential of students, the solution of this problem has been activated in the educational process in all structures of public education. There are attempts to develop the growing generation, including outside the classroom, in various humanitarian circles, societies, spiritually, intellectually and creatively. Not only, extracurricular activities to study the historical and cultural heritage of the Uzbek people, but also other peoples will be a priority. In relation to the creative-intellectual-creative development of elementary school students, in relation to similar activities in the process of learning the history and culture of their own country, other countries and peoples outside the classroom - systematic-pedagogical approach, intensive pedagogical technologies, effective methods, there is a need for the most convenient methods and methods.

As long as the history of Uzbekistan is studied in the educational process, the interest in the history and culture of Uzbekistan is of special importance in the students. In the content of school textbooks, national-cultural monuments are mentioned and even discussed, including ancient-architectural monuments, which arouses the interest of students to study them more deeply. As long as at this age, first of all, important intellectual and creative qualities and abilities are formed, developed and improved, it relies on the necessary information. The main thing is that the intellectual-creative potential, which is necessary in any sphere of the life and activity of the builder of a new society, is formed - the universal aspect of a modern person.

The problem of logic is the problem of truth, the cognitive connection of thinking with existence. The problem of the science of psychology is to study the flow of the thinking process, the mental activity of a person, the specific relationship of thinking with other aspects of consciousness. The psychology of thinking and the science of logic, which differ from each other in content, are closely related at the same time.

The task of psychological research of thinking and its development is to reveal mental activity as a process and, if possible, to identify its patterns. According to this task, learning to develop the mental activity of students is also seen in the educational process.

In psychological and pedagogical literature, there are several classifications of types of thinking that describe certain stages of the development of thinking. Let's name the main ones.

This happens not only in humans (mainly in preschool children), but also in "higher" animals, and in cases where problem solving is carried out with the help of a real change in the situation with the help of an observed motor movement.

Thus, the creative-intellectual-creative activity of students has socio-pedagogical importance and is a self-evident factor in the development and improvement of the basic qualities and abilities of a person of the modern generation who has the criteria of a perfect person. is considered to be New, most convenient forms, methods, means, and methods of education are needed. In this regard, we should quickly prepare a methodology based on national characteristics. Of course, knowing, perceiving, thinking, reflecting, summarizing, at the intellectual-creative level of speech communication is carried out not only by historical-cultural, but also by cultural, including public communication knowledge, norms and rules.

It should be said that the problems of spiritual, moral and educational education are currently being researched, which consists of: loyalty to universal values, strengthening and development of the spiritual heritage of our people, and free manifestation of one's potential.

Great ancestors - philosophers-thinkers: Al-Khorazmi, Imam Bukhari, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Khoja Ahmed Yassavi, Alisher Navai, Ogahi, etc. and also XIX-XX centuries Pedagogical thoughts and opinions of scientists such as Behbudi, Avloni, Fitrat form the basis of cultural and educational education, which is a reliable factor in the formation of a modern mature personality. [1. B. 31-61]

The use of folk pedagogy has become more active in the spiritual, intellectual and creative development of students. It remains traditional to stage folk tales based on the appropriate interior conditions and the use of clothes of fairy-tale characters, folklore conversations, singing folk songs, telling riddles and finding their meaning, proverbs on a certain topic and with the organization of a competition on the knowledge of matals, parties are organized in which heroes of fairy tales are dressed in masquerade (theatre) clothes, folklore conferences of folk songs, etc. are held.

The development of creative personality of students in all structures of the modern education system is a socio-pedagogical problem of state importance. The issue of solving it is defined in the national pedagogic science. There are attempts to research such important creative abilities of students based on intellectual and creative, including national historical and cultural values. However, pedagogically, it has not been completed to a sufficiently reasonable level.

Scientific-pedagogical work on the creative development of students, as well as intellectual-creative, for such important creative abilities intended for this age, has not been sufficiently researched until now. It is known from many years of observation that students have

a great interest and active desire to know them, including in excursion conditions, in the process of studying the historical-cultural ancient-architectural monuments of Uzbekistan outside the classroom. There are insufficient levels of possible episodic communication with foreign tourists about the grandeur, beauty, national-architectural features of ancient-architectural art in English. However, it is necessary for students to study the ancient architectural monuments of Uzbekistan from a creative historical-cultural and artistic-aesthetic point of view.

We find it necessary to study the following concepts and categories when considering and defining the main principles of creative abilities: creative, creativity; intellect, intellectual activity - basic structures, content; intellect - thinking - types, forms; creativity - essence, structural-level components, scheme and technology; abilities - creative, intellectual-creative abilities - as a complex of creative qualities, their priorities; creative imagination, its development, requirements for it; intellectual-creative process, its basis, main components, conditions; intellectual-creative activity - its types.

We pay attention to the definition of the concepts and terms "Competence" and "competence" in dictionaries, with the intention of better understanding, identifying their differences and similarities: The dictionary meaning of the concept of competence is explained in different languages as follows: - Competent (in French) - authorized; - Competent (in Latin) – capable; - Competent (in English) - capable. In the "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" it is interpreted as follows: competence - knowledge, experience in one or another field.

Creative - "creatio" -Latin - the ability to create, to create, to generate unusual ideas, to deviate from the traditional schemes of thinking, to quickly solve problematic situations. In short, the focus of creativity is on the topic of creativity. In psychology, this concept is in two directions: - the life experience and individual characteristics of a creative person (personality factors); creative thinking and its products (factors of creativity - consistency of thinking, accuracy, changeability, sensitivity to problems, originality, ingenuity, constructiveness in finding their solution) are considered. [2. 39-40 b]

Creativity (English - "creativity") is an ability that reflects the deep nature of individuals to create unique values, make non-standard, creative decisions.

A non-standard and creative solution is created in the process of new, unique, intellectual-creative activity - on the basis of active perception and creative uplifting spirit "in the complete concentration of all spiritual forces in the object of creation, emotional multiplicity the state of being tarinki is understood.

Creativity is a variety of emotions, communication, thinking, activity types of creative talents. It is a creative process of generating ideas and creating various "products". It is understood as a critical attitude towards new ideas, a critical attitude towards new ideas. [4. 112-113b]

Today, creativity is perceived as a stable personality function that depends on a complex of characteristics. It was noted that there are many opportunities to solve the problem of extracurricular work, especially on the basis of national and world historical and cultural artistic material. Therefore, the main issue in the development of creativity is to determine personal qualities. It is because of them that a person shows himself. Creativity includes sensitivity to specific problems, lack of information. Creativity is expressive and verbal.

The main criteria of creative abilities: variability (relating to intelligence, thinking), oneness (the number of ideas per unit of time), originality (relating to thinking, new ideas), metaphoricity (unusuality, strangeness, associativeness), perception, sensitivity (divided into

ideas, ideas, details, etc. All this develops on the basis of necessary motivation. In this case, the following skills are also included: curiosity (ability to wonder, thoroughness, openness), precision (ability to clarify thinking), improvement, completion of the creative product, boldness (regarding solutions and conclusions).

Thus, creative abilities are a factor of high creative development, creative expressions in various types of activity, for example, speech, writing and many other types. It is worth noting that the development of creative abilities of students, first of all, requires a personality-oriented approach, emotional-psychic mood, self-activation - independence, self- - requires control - demonstration - expression - assessment, technology, natural state, active thinking - creative imagination. Thanks to this, it is possible to develop the logical competencies of future primary school teachers.

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